

Features of Some Clinical, Social and Criminological Parameters in People with an Atypical Picture of Acute Alcohol Poisoning

Turayev Bobir Temirpulotovich

Assistant of the department of psychiatry, medical psychology and narcology, Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhadov Arslonbek A'zamjon ugli, Abilov Saidfirdavs Bakhtiyor ugli,

Yangabayev Shakhzodbek Ganibay ugli

Samarkand State Medical University Faculty of medicine №2, 605-Group student, Samarkand, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: In Clinical Psychiatry, among the various types of acute intoxication with psychoactive substances, the concept of atypical alcohol intoxication stands out. In these cases, compared to the usual clinical picture, an increase in the group of symptoms or the sequence of their occurrence changes, or various mental disorders appear that are not typical of typical cases of alcohol poisoning.

Keywords: Alcohol poisoning, chronic alcoholism, clinical, social and criminological parameters.

Introduction. Many previous studies have shown that alcohol poisoning is one of the main factors that cause illegal behavior. According to local authors, 70,2% of violent crimes were committed in the case of alcohol poisoning; 72,2% of murders, 64% of sex crimes, 57% of domestic violence cases, and 54% of child abuse cases [1-4].

According to foreign studies, more than half of the crimes committed involved alcohol consumption: 50% murder; 15% robbery, 26% robbery and 37% rape [5].

The high criminogenic potential of the state of alcohol is usually associated with the following effect of alcohol on the human body: - disinhibition effect on the emotional-voluntary sphere; - effect on critical and predictive abilities; - to facilitate the implementation of hidden, compensated aggressive tendencies that are not controlled in the case of alcohol poisoning due to the weakness of voluntary mechanisms and violations of critical and predictive functions [6-9].

However, many researchers argue that, in normal cases, a person's state of intoxication due to a largely inhibitory effect on the central nervous system not only does not stimulate, but also prevents the formation of aggressive behavior, including illegal behavior [10-12]. It is noted that the increase in illegal activity in alcohol poisoning is associated not with alcohol intoxication, but with the formation of its atypical clinical picture [13].

In contrast to "normal" alcohol poisoning, which is characterized by a sequential change in the relatively short period of stimulation of mental activity, with its Depression, a longer period of sedation [14], the state of intoxication is considered atypical in the absence of the indicated two-phase dynamics of its clinical picture [15].

The two-phase effect inherent in ethanol has been confirmed by electroencephalographic and psychophysiological research methods [16]. Often, the clinical picture of alcohol poisoning is considered atypical in its composition with emotional-volitional and cognitive disorders, depth and psychopathological appearance of mental disorders, delusion of perception, the development of

delusional disorders, which is often one of the reasons for absurd and abnormal behavior that is not inherent in the personality structure of the accused and suspect [17-21].

The development of an atypical clinical picture of alcohol poisoning is usually associated with "temporary" or "permanent" soil effects [22]. "Temporary" soil environment factors are often defined by various psychogenies, psychophysical overwork, acute viral infections, and "permanent soil" factors include mature personality disorder, organic mental illness, and the presence of alcohol dependence [23-27].

Chronic alcoholism allows you to observe how clinical manifestations change over time within the framework of one disease, including a picture of alcohol poisoning, which gradually becomes "atypical". In fact, this "atypicality" is natural and is a characteristic symptom of an advanced stage of chronic alcoholism, appearing after the onset of amnesic forms of alcohol and often continuing in parallel with the growth of personality changes, varying depending on the explosion and dysphoricity [28-33].

In addition to patients with chronic alcoholism, the widest group showing atypicality of intoxication is the contingent of those with organic mental illness. Alcohol consumption enhances the irritability, exploitation, dysphoric disorders inherent in these individuals, which dramatically changes and aggravates the picture of acute alcohol intoxication, which often does not fall within the framework of the standard idea of normal intoxication [34-37]. Chronic alcoholism (especially traumatic brain injuries) is common among people with organic brain pathology despite being poorly tolerated compared to alcohol.

Complex forms of intoxication are characteristic symptoms of Psycho-organic syndrome [38-41]. Masts "affective instability", weak resistance to affective stimuli, inconsistency between objective cause and reaction attract attention. Therefore, in the case of alcohol poisoning, violence, aggressive behavior towards others is common [42-48]. Often socially dangerous behavior occurs in a state of intoxication with epileptoid alcohol intoxication and exploitation [49-53].

Some researchers have studied the acute and chronic effects of alcohol and their effects on the commission of violent crimes, concluding that the manifestation of acute alcohol poisoning, not the presence (or absence) of alcoholism, is associated with Real illegal behavior, and alcohol directly contributes to the manifestation of violence [54-60]. At the same time, other authors, having studied this problem, attach sufficient importance to the fact of Alcohol Dependence, the presence of which clearly affects the cruelty and severity of crimes and criminal recidivism. The study of the effect of alcohol on delinquent behavior determines the significantly important role of acute intoxication of alcohol in the period of the crime, the presence of alcohol dependence and other psychosocial factors, such as negative psychobiographic circumstances, criminal past, etc. alcohol intoxication directly contributes to violent crimes and is related to their cruelty and severity [61-65].

The purpose of the study characteristics of some clinical, social and criminological parameters in people with atypical manifestations of acute alcohol poisoning

Materials and methods. We examined 109 men aged 18 to 60 who underwent inpatient forensic psychiatric examination from 2004 to 2020, who identified signs of organic mental disorders of various origins, as well as some atypical forms of alcohol poisoning during illegal behavior and Anamnesis.

Individuals with clinical signs of alcohol dependence were dominated by middle and older individuals (55,3%) in this group of 67 people, half of whom were married and had children (53,7%), incomplete middle (25,4%) and middle (56,7%) with physical education education (52,2%), including low-skilled (20,9%) labor. Of those tested, 6% were diagnosed with somatic disease-induced disability and 14,9% were diagnosed: "Organic brain damage", including mental retardation. Those who served in the military during the term accounted for half of those who were examined, were exempted from serving in the army due to organic mental disorders and personality disorders - 22.4%, the rest were not serving due to previous convictions, or were exempt from somatic disease Service (11,9%). Almost

half (50,7%) of this contingent have been criminally prosecuted in the past, mainly against property offenses (theft, robbery – 26,9%) and against public order and security (acts of bullying, alimony evasion, etc).

Research results and discussion. In the case of mental disorders in this group, hereditary weight was observed in 32,8% of cases, in the case of alcoholism – in 43,8% of cases. Developmental disorders were found in 18% of those examined, and disc fractures in 16.7% (mostly in the form of negligence). In most cases (43,3%) by the age of 18, personal characteristics were formed according to the excitatory type, in 28,4% - the degree of severity of psychopathic-like disorders of organic Genesis reached the depth of psychopathy. Antisociality and antisociality were characteristic of 44,8 percent of this contingent, with a low percentage (1,5 percent) of "hypersociality". More than half (55,2%) of adults have severe or chronic somatic diseases, 83,6% have head injuries, mostly recurrent. Variants of the leading organic syndrome developed as follows: psychopathic-like (58,2%), cerebrastrhenic (16,4%), paroxysmal (10,4%), intellectual-Mnestic disorders (7,5%), affective (4,5%), neurosis-like (3,0%).

The statistical probability relationship is significantly determined between the age of the first alcohol samples and parameters such as the stage of alcoholism (correlation coefficient $r=0.77$; $p<0,001$). The same significant correlation ($R=0.41$; $p< 0,01$) was reported between hereditary weight levels and progredience levels of alcoholism.

Almost a third of the subjects (31,3%) had an alcoholic psychosis, mainly a delirium structure. Two-thirds (61,2%) were previously treated with drugs. In this group of those examined, psychotic forms of alcohol were recorded in 39,1% of cases (among them there are the following options: Hallucinator, delirium, paranoid, derealization-depersonalization, Twilight consciousness Disorders, pathological waking state before exiting intoxication), with motor disorders-4,7% (hyperkinetic symptom complex, epileptiform seizures, psychomotor arousal), affective-17,2% (dysthymic variant, manic, Fear Effect), psychopathic-like — At 85,9% (variants: form with elements of exploitative, dysphoric, hysteroid, paranoid, arousal disorder, delusional delusions and eidetism). The above statistics reflect the presence of different atypical forms of intoxication in the same subject. Here the frequency of occurrence of each form is given, and therefore their sum is not equal to 100%.

The most common factors of temporary pathological soil in force on the eve of committing a crime were cases of alcoholism (41,8%), psychogenic factor (17,9%), which included the effects of long - term stress (tense relationships in the family, death of relatives, serious illness of family members-1,5%.) and psychogenism, before criminal acts (41,8%).scandal, insult-16,4%). The presence of temporary asthenization factors is clearly observed in 70,1% of cases.

Under the influence of exogenous-organic damage, including chronic alcohol intoxication, the characteristic features developed mainly in terms of the exploitative (68,7%) and dysthymic (10,4%) variants.

In this group, 20,9% of subjects were found to be insane due to the level of violence of organic diseases and psychoses, which individuals were recommended for mandatory treatment in a psychiatric hospital. According to expert conclusions, 53,7% of subjects needed medical coercion measures against alcoholism. Forensic Psychiatric conclusions regarding individuals with clinical signs of stage I of alcoholism often give a category of "alcohol abuse tendency" and do not recommend medical coercion measures. Surveillance in prisons by a psychiatrist (neuropsychologist) was recommended in 6,0% of cases, mainly in connection with epileptiform diseases.

Individuals with no clinical signs of alcohol dependence were dominated by young and middle-aged individuals (90,5%) between the ages of 18 and 46 in this group of 42. About half (59%) were married and had children, and received secondary and secondary special education (61,9%) which involved skilled physical labor. 2,4% of those tested had a disability due to somatic disease, while 2,4% of those tested for mental illness. Less than half (40,5%) of individuals in this group served in the military on a term basis, while 33,3% were exempted from serving in the army due to organic brain pathology and

personality disorders. 4,8% were exempt from somatic disease (4,8%), either due to previous convictions or for other reasons (the only breadwinner in the family). A large proportion (40,5%) of those investigated by this group have been criminalised in the past mainly in the case of severe illegal acts against the individual (murder, serious bodily injury, rape — 41,2%).

In this group of mental disorders, hereditary weight was recorded in 28,9% of cases, in alcoholism-in 48,9% of cases. Developmental disorders were observed in 26% of those examined, and disc disorders in 14,3%. Among the types of personality traits formed by the age of 18, asthenic (28,6%) and excitatory (26,2%) types prevailed. Severe psychopathic-like syndrome occurred in 23,8% of cases. 35,7% of those examined reported antisocial and antisocial behavior, and 16,7% reported "hypersociality". Severe and chronic somatic diseases in adulthood have been observed in 42,9% of cases. Head injuries in 66,7% of cases. Variants of the leading organic syndrome in this group are expressed as follows: psychopathic-like (38,1%), cerebrasthenic (26,2%), neurosis-like (11,9%), affective (9,5%), intellectual and Mnestic disorders (7,1%), paroxysmal disease syndrome (4,8%), disc disorder (2,4%).

The latter also manifested as a joint syndrome. In this group of those examined, movement disorders in the composition of acute intoxication of alcohol were reported in 8.9% of cases, psychotic - in 31,1%, affective - in 22,2%, psychopathic - in 66,7%.

The leading factor in temporary pathological soil was psychogenic (28.6%). The presence of additional damage was observed in 45,8% of cases.

Under the influence of exogenous-organic damage, the characteristic changes developed mainly on the exploitative variant (45,2%), while asthenic (23,8%) and dysthymic (19,0%) variants were also important.

Individuals who were exculpated accounted for 38,1% of those examined by this group. Among them, mandatory treatment in a psychiatric hospital was recommended in 26,2% of cases, PND follow-up in 11,9% of cases (when a temporary painful mental illness was diagnosed during OOD). 2,4% of those tested for mandatory treatment against alcoholism, when observed by a psychiatrist (neuropsychologist) in places of deprivation of Liberty - 19,0% of subjects.

Conclusions. Comparing the two groups of those examined, a significantly larger proportion of people with hereditary severity in mental disorders are identified among alcohol addicts, while the hereditary severity in alcoholism is the same in both groups.

In the first group, the excitatory type of personality traits prevailed, in the second, the excitatory and asthenic occupied almost equal parts, with a slight predominance of the latter.

In people with alcohol dependence, as a rule, a progressive type of organic pathology, a significant severity of neurological diseases during the examination period, epileptiform syndrome are often noted. Among those examined without signs of alcoholism, a residual stable state prevails due to organic brain damage.

The depth of personality disorders of organic origin, as well as driver disorders, turned out to be almost equal in both groups. Developmental abnormalities prevailed among individuals who were not addicted to alcohol.

In the first group of puberty, the frequency of somatic diseases and head injuries exceeded the indicator in the second group. Comparison of the percentage of different variants of atypical alcohol poisoning in comparative groups showed the predominance of psychotic and psychopathic-like forms of alcohol poisoning in people with symptoms of chronic alcoholism.

And motor and affective options are a little more common in those who do not have this disease. Thus, with the development of alcoholism, on the one hand, the likelihood of developing atypical forms of alcohol poisoning increased, with a tendency to appear psychotic variants of it, on the other hand, personal changes with signs of alcohol degradation increased. Both in a state of intoxication, his

atypism was a risk factor for committing severe offenses that played a key role, and these or other personal violations and antisocial tendencies came to the fore.

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